

A NOTE ON CERTAIN HETEROCYCLIC SULPHONAMIDES

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In continuation of our previous investigations (Choudhury, Das-Gupta and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 733; De and Basu, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1938, **26**, 537, Basu and Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 301) 2-sulphanilamido-4-methyl (Fosbinder and Walter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2032), and 2-sulphanilamido-3: 4-tetrahydrobenzothiazoles, and 4-sulphanilamido-1-phenyl-2:3-dimethyl-5-pyrazolone (Roblin, Williams and English, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 2002) have been prepared. But two of the above three compounds have already been published by the above authors. The method of preparation of the sulphamethylthiazole being somewhat different from that published and the tetrahydrobenzothiazole derivative being undescribed, our observations in this connection are recorded here. It has been found that neither the tetrahydrobenzothiazole, nor the sulphanilamidopyrazolone shows any activity against experimental pneumococcal (Type I) infections in white mice. The pharmacological investigations have been carried out by Dr. A. Bose and will be reported in detail elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Amino-3:4-tetrahydrobenzothiazole.—2-Chlorocyclohexanone (1 mol.) and thiourea (1 mol.) were refluxed in absolute alcoholic solution for 1 hour and the alcohol distilled off. The residue was dissolved in water and the solution made strongly alkaline with potassium carbonate and extracted with ether. On evaporating the ether, the compound was isolated as a semi-solid mass, which was then converted into its hydrochloride by treating with hydrochloric acid. It separated as colourless crystals from rectified spirit, m.p. 243-44°. (Found: N, 14.04; Cl, 18.31. $C_7H_{10}N_2S$, HCl, requires N, 14.7; Cl, 18.63 per cent.)

2-(p-Acetylamino-benzenesulphonamido)-3:4-tetrahydrobenzothiazole.—A solution of 2-aminotetrahydrobenzothiazole (3 g.) and p-acetylamino-benzenesulphonyl chloride (2 g.) in pyridine was left overnight. After distilling off the pyridine the residue was washed with cold water and the compound obtained as buff-coloured microscopic crystals from a mixture of

alcohol and water (1:4), melting indefinitely at 180° . (Found: N, 11.2; H_2O , 4.7. $C_{15}H_{17}O_2N_3S_2$, H_2O requires N, 11.38; H_2O , 4.88 per cent).

2-Sulphanilamido-3:4-tetrahydrobenzothiazole.—*p*-Acetylamino benzene-sulphonamido-tetrahydrobenzothiazole (1 g.) was heated with aqueous alcoholic hydrochloric acid (5%, 20 c.c.) for 25 minutes. After treating the mixture as in the previous case, the compound was isolated as buff-coloured microscopic crystals from dilute alcohol, m.p. $150-54^{\circ}$ (indifferent). (Found: N, 12.72; H_2O , 5.42. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2N_3S_2$, H_2O requires N, 12.84; H_2O , 5.5 per cent). The compound gives diazo reaction and is soluble in both acids and alkalis.

2-Sulphanilamido-4-methylthiazole.—A solution of *p*-acetylamino benzene-sulphonyl chloride (1 mol.) and 4-methylthiazole (2 mol.) in dry ethyl acetate was left overnight. The solvent was evaporated off and the residue obtained on treatment with cold water afforded the 2-(*p*-acetylamino benzene-sulphonamido)-4-methylthiazole already described by Fosbinder and Walter (*loc. cit.*) in a crystalline form. This product was hydrolysed by heating on a steam-bath with 5% hydrochloric acid in 50% alcohol (20 c.c. for 1 g.). The mixture was diluted with water and neutralised with ammonia in cold. The solid, separating, was isolated as buff-coloured microscopic crystals from 50% alcohol, m.p. $236-37^{\circ}$, yield 50% of the weight of the acetyl derivative. (Found: N, 15.45. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_3S_2$, requires N, 15.61 per cent).